

APPLYING ROLE-PLAYING GAMES IN EFL CLASSES TO THE CULTURE-ORIENTED LINGUISTICS APPROACH

Munira X.Xakimova

senior teacher of history and philology faculty, foreign languages and literature department, Tashkent University for Applied Sciences, Tashkent-Uzbekistan,
email: munirakhakimova2575@gmail.com

Annotation: The focus of the article is on how the linguocultural approach is being used in EFL classes. The importance of the linguo-cultural approach in the development of students' intercultural communication skills and preparation is made clear. The role-playing approach, which has enormous educational and educational potential and is regarded as a model of interaction and communication, is given a lot of attention. The key findings from observing the students' role-play performances revealed that role-play as a teaching technique can boost speaking and communication skills, foster a supportive environment for active learning, encourage collaboration, enhance cultural understanding, enhance problem-solving and critical thinking skills, as well as make learning more engaging and memorable. Consequently, role-play not only enhances language instruction but also cultivates positive behaviors, attitudes, and overall student engagement with learning beyond English.

Key words: linguistic and cultural approach, role-playing games, motivation, interest, foreign language communication, intercultural communication, the humanistic paradigm of education, orienting, compensating.

1. Introduction

Today's foreign language teaching methodologies, both local and international, acknowledge the necessity for pupils to learn a foreign language while also becoming familiar with the country's culture, history, and contemporary way of life. Much of this has to do with tasks creation of a graduate's harmonious personality, who must be prepared for integration into a communication context that supports diversity. It is also related to the idea that "the humanistic paradigm of education, which places the student's moral growth, his intellectual demands, and his interpersonal relationships in first place, is brought to the fore by the reinforcement of humanistic ideals in modern society as a priority" [1]. Every culture in the nation has a language. Teaching English should therefore be closely related to the cultural characteristics of the English speaking countries. An intercultural approach combines cultural and linguistic skills. The article gives a summary of the literature on important ideas as approaches to the meaning and component structure of intercultural communicative competence; it discusses the specifics of using gaming technology in the context of teaching foreign languages; it suggests assessment standards for English language textbooks on the implementation of the intercultural approach; it analyzes English-language textbooks; it evaluates students' levels of intercultural competence; it develops a gaming technology complex to improve intercultural communication skills; and it conducts experiments to develop intercultural communication skills.

2. Literature review.

The study of linguistic and cultural material aids in the foreign language learner's comprehension of the national-historical characteristics present in various sociocultural contexts. In addition, because language serves as a medium of communication as well as a means of accumulation, it also serves as a source of knowledge about the history and culture of his nation. As stated by E. I. Passova, "the goal of education is that part of the general culture of mankind, which the student can master in the process of communicative foreign language education in cognitive (linguo-cultural), developing (psychological), educational

(pedagogical), and educational (social) aspects." A foreign language also brings with it a foreign language culture [2]. Relying on this point of view, it should be noted that the process of teaching foreign languages aims to develop students' unique ability to participate in direct and indirect dialogue of cultures, improve knowledge of a foreign language and use it in the process of studying various fields of science and public life. The linguistic and regional approach is relevant at any stage of teaching a foreign language, since today "the importance of learning is rising to a new level. foreign language, which is the most important means of forming students sociocultural competence, which includes respect for languages, traditions and culture of other nations" [3]. It should be emphasized that students learn about the realities, mores, customs, and traditions of the country whose language they are learning as well as the necessary communicative behavior in verbal communication and skills of competent verbal and non-verbal behavior in specific situations on the basis of the socio-cultural component of teaching a foreign language. The findings of our study demonstrate that both schoolchildren and students exhibit a genuine, alive interest in the lives of their peers in the nations where the language being learned is spoken, in their customs, traditions, way of life, and modes of recreation. The playful language teaching methodology is a particular teaching methodology that consists of teaching languages by using game-based exercises, and it has been found to be particularly effective especially in multi-ethnic contexts. It is founded on the humanistic-affective approach and consists of educational paths and language teaching techniques based on games. Indeed, the playful language teaching methodology shares the same goals with the humanistic-affective approach, as it aims to eliminate learning obstacles such as stress or anxiety, it works on long-term memory and considers learners' emotional involvement. According to Caon and Rutka, the playful language teaching methodology realises, through different types of game-based techniques, the founding principles of the humanistic-affective approach, that can be recognized in five fundamental principles:

- a) attention to students' communicative needs regarding the psycho-affective and motivational components that influence the learning;
- b) importance of languages as instruments of self-expression and social interaction with particular attention to socio-cultural, intercultural, para- and extra-linguistic aspects;
- c) idea of learning as a constructive process in which learners must be actively engaged in the construction of their knowledge, which takes place by connecting what is learnt with prior knowledge;
- d) awareness and appreciation of the differences between learners arising from their personal history, their social environment, their specific interests, their existential and scholastic objectives, their cognitive and learning styles;
- e) concept of teachers' role as learning facilitators rather than just content communicators.

Despite the many prejudices that still exist about this specific methodology by both teachers and students, the use of games encourages learners to deal with language learning in a natural and comfortable way, allowing them to employ all their cognitive, emotive, social, and sensory skills. Therefore, the game-based methodology consists of the transmission of grammatical and lexical contents in the form of games by avoiding learner pressure and promoting student learning. In addition, the wealth of stimuli contained in this type of activity increases not only students' attention, but also their motivation towards the subject studied .

3.Results and discussion

The use of methods and tools for working with students that are designed to increase their capacity and readiness to implement intercultural communication at a high enough level becomes relevant in the process of teaching a foreign language, of course, within the framework of the implementation of the linguo-cultural approach. One of these types of work is a role-playing game, which, as a contemporary interactive way of teaching a foreign language in the implementation of the linguo-cultural approach, accomplishes the primary learning tasks of motivation and incentive, instruction, education, orienting,

and compensating. By using a linguistic and cultural approach to the selection and organization of educational material, it is anticipated that at this stage of foreign language teaching, educational, educational, and developmental orientation of the content of training will be strengthened. This approach helps to assimilate a foreign language in close connection with culture and history of his country.

Without using examples of acceptable speech behavior in specific situations, in isolation from knowledge of reality and the culture of the country where the language being studied, it is impossible to prepare students for effective foreign language communication and to form their communicative abilities. In actuality, it happens frequently that linguistic and cultural ignorance rather than a communicant's limited proficiency in a foreign language is the cause of difficulties in the process of communication and mutual understanding between representatives of other cultures. It is undeniable in this regard that local knowledge should contribute to the extension of background knowledge. In this regard, we believe that when imparting linguistic and regional knowledge, students' motivation is formed. The essence of this motivation, which develops in the absence of a foreign language environment, is their emotional and personal attitude toward the nation and people of the language being studied.

The use of role-playing games in foreign language schools is currently enough of a topic of significant interest, as our observations have demonstrated. Since they are based on the desire to act in an imagined situation with an open ending and the potential for an interesting development of the plot, language at a university allows modeling real situations of cross-cultural communication while taking into account the linguistic and cultural specifics of communication. This is why students are so interested in them [4]. Moreover, role-playing the game fits readily into the classroom and makes learning enjoyable for students as a model for interpersonal group contact and a unique organizational style of teaching oral-speech communication based on the communicative principle. As correctly noted by S. V. Efimenko, "a modern student transforms from a passive element of the educational system into an active participant in the educational process" when using role-playing games in the classroom to learn a foreign language [5]. Role-playing games are, thus, quite common and are used to tackle challenging issues with learning new information, strengthening and developing creative abilities, as well as for the development of general educational skills. We concur with N. M. Tarasova that "a foreign language culture consisting by themselves, sociocultural elements contribute to learning motivation, the development of demands and interests, and a more deliberate study of a foreign language [6]. As a result, using an interactive method like a role-playing game by the teacher while using the linguistic and cultural approach helps students become more motivated to study a foreign language in depth and with more awareness based on their own country's history and culture. All of this aids in the emergence and growth of students' sustained cognitive interest in the socioculturally mediated aspects of the foreign language they are learning. Let's use a role-playing game as an illustration of how the linguistic and cultural approach is put into practice in a university foreign language classroom.

The participants of the game, a group of 10 people, receive specific roles in the activity "Literary newspaper," which is most appropriate to carry out in the context of the topic "Peculiarities of the cultural life of the country of the language being studied." The students are then free to choose the role they prefer. We suggested a cast of characters that included the magazine's editor-in-chief, two journalists, two writers for the "Letters readers" feature, four readers, and one person who has never been a fan of literature or similar journals. Each participant game receives a task matching to the character after the roles have been distributed. Also, the magazine's presentation will feature a special visitor who dislikes literature. He is creating a list of arguments against a literary journal. He must ultimately make the decision regarding the necessity of such a log. The teacher's role in the game is creative and instructive. The game's lesson is comprised of the following. First-year students' vocabulary is tested orally, which encourages them to use already-familiar words, focus on the lesson, and get ready for the next activity. All players are offered the same options during the game's initial phase. In order to ensure that the presentation is organized rationally, the editor-in-chief provides prepared questions for the presentation to

each of his colleagues. The writers of the "Letters readers" column receive letters that readers have already prepared and start to process them in writing. As a response, journalists poll readers and "independent" experts to learn how people feel about literature in general and about their favorite authors in particular. After the preliminary phase, the new magazine is shown. The editor-in-chief is the first to speak, and he also determines the order in which all other statements will be delivered. An expert with a viewpoint will offer one at the conclusion of the session. An evaluation of all the work completed is done collectively at the conclusion of the game, and each student's involvement is rated. One of the most striking examples of a role-playing game that has its own screenplay and requires meticulous planning beforehand is this one.

4. Conclusion

Students enjoy these games because they are imaginative and they are very successful at helping pupils retain previously learned linguo-cultural material. The aforementioned example demonstrates the benefits of role-playing games, including the development of communication scenarios in foreign language lessons and their emphasis on boosting students' enthusiasm to study a foreign language. As can be seen from our example, in a role-playing game, consciousness is formed belonging of its participants to the team, interconnection of participants is built when solving common problems, as well as developing logical thinking, the ability to search for answers to the questions posed, the ability to communicate with each other and find the most effective communication strategies, since "business games contribute to the formation of communicative competence [7].

Since role-playing games have considerable teaching and educational qualities and may be viewed as an exact model of interaction and communication, they can thus correctly be attributed to being the most successful way to work with students in the educational process of higher education. In the context of implementing the linguistic and regional approach in the university, role-playing games have a significant advantage over other communicative exercises in that they imply the imitation of reality in its most fundamental features, strengthening the personal involvement of students in the game's subject.

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